

Supplementary Materials for: Flow-based Policy With Distributional Reinforcement Learning

Ruijie Hao^{1,2}, Longfei Zhang^{1,2}, Yang Dai^{1,2}, Yang Ma³, Xingxing Liang^{1,2*},
and Guangquan Cheng^{1,2*}

¹ College of Systems Engineering, National University of Defense Technology,
Changsha 410073, China

² Laboratory for Big Data and Decision, National University of Defense Technology,
Changsha 410073, China

³ Aviation University of Air Force, Changchun 130000, China

Abstract. This supplementary material provides theoretical support and comprehensive implementation details for the main paper “Flow-based Policy With Distributional Reinforcement Learning.” Section A presents a formal proof of the contraction property for the distributional Bellman operator under the maximal Wasserstein-2 distance, establishing the theoretical convergence guarantee of the quantile-based critic. Section B describes the six MuJoCo continuous control tasks (Ant-v4, HalfCheetah-v4, Hopper-v4, Humanoid-v4, InvertedPendulum-v4, and Reacher-v4) used in the empirical evaluation, including their state-action spaces and reward structures. Section C elaborates on the algorithmic implementation, covering the quantile critic architecture with IQN-style embedding, the Transformer-based continuous normalizing flow actor with exact divergence computation, batch renormalization strategies, and automatic entropy tuning. Section D tabulates the complete hyperparameter configuration for FP-DRL, including general training settings, critic and actor network specifications, and entropy regularization coefficients. Together, these sections ensure full reproducibility and supplement the theoretical and experimental results reported in the main text.

A Proof of lemma

Lemma 1 *The distributional Bellman operator \mathcal{T}^π is a γ -contraction under the maximal W_2 distance \bar{d}_{W_2} . That is, for any two distributions $Z_1, Z_2 \in \mathcal{Z}$:*

$$\bar{d}_{W_2}(\mathcal{T}^\pi Z_1, \mathcal{T}^\pi Z_2) \leq \gamma \bar{d}_{W_2}(Z_1, Z_2). \quad (1)$$

Proof. Consider any two distribution functions $Z_1, Z_2 \in \mathcal{Z}$. By the definition of the maximal metric \bar{d}_{W_2} , we have:

$$\bar{d}_{W_2}(\mathcal{T}^\pi Z_1, \mathcal{T}^\pi Z_2) = \sup_{s,a} W_2(\mathcal{T}^\pi Z_1(s, a), \mathcal{T}^\pi Z_2(s, a)). \quad (2)$$

Recall that the distributional Bellman operator is defined as $\mathcal{T}^\pi Z(s, a) \stackrel{D}{=} R(s, a) + \gamma P^\pi Z(s, a)$, where $P^\pi Z(s, a)$ represents the distribution of the value at the next state.

By the properties of the Wasserstein metric W_2 , specifically **shift invariance** regarding the reward $R(s, a)$ and **homogeneity** of degree 1 regarding the scalar γ , we derive:

$$\begin{aligned} W_2(\mathcal{T}^\pi Z_1(s, a), \mathcal{T}^\pi Z_2(s, a)) &= W_2(R(s, a) + \gamma P^\pi Z_1(s, a), R(s, a) + \gamma P^\pi Z_2(s, a)) \\ &= W_2(\gamma P^\pi Z_1(s, a), \gamma P^\pi Z_2(s, a)) \\ &= \gamma W_2(P^\pi Z_1(s, a), P^\pi Z_2(s, a)). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Now we consider the transition operator P^π . Since the squared Wasserstein metric W_2^2 is convex with respect to mixtures (i.e., $W_2^2(\sum w_i \mu_i, \sum w_i \nu_i) \leq \sum w_i W_2^2(\mu_i, \nu_i)$), we have:

$$\begin{aligned} W_2^2(P^\pi Z_1(s, a), P^\pi Z_2(s, a)) &\leq \mathbb{E}_{s', a' \sim P, \pi} [W_2^2(Z_1(s', a'), Z_2(s', a'))] \\ &\leq \sup_{s', a'} W_2^2(Z_1(s', a'), Z_2(s', a')) \\ &= \bar{d}_{W_2}^2(Z_1, Z_2). \end{aligned}$$

Taking the square root of both sides yields:

$$W_2(P^\pi Z_1(s, a), P^\pi Z_2(s, a)) \leq \bar{d}_{W_2}(Z_1, Z_2). \quad (4)$$

Combining (3) and (4) with (2), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{d}_{W_2}(\mathcal{T}^\pi Z_1, \mathcal{T}^\pi Z_2) &= \sup_{s, a} W_2(\mathcal{T}^\pi Z_1(s, a), \mathcal{T}^\pi Z_2(s, a)) \\ &\leq \gamma \sup_{s, a} W_2(P^\pi Z_1(s, a), P^\pi Z_2(s, a)) \\ &\leq \gamma \bar{d}_{W_2}(Z_1, Z_2). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, \mathcal{T}^π is a γ -contraction in \bar{d}_{W_2} .

B Detailed Environment Descriptions

We evaluate our method on the continuous control tasks from the MuJoCo physics engine. Detailed descriptions of the tasks are provided below to facilitate reproducibility. The state usually consists of the position and velocity of the joint and the action controls the torque applied to the joint.

- **Ant-v4**: A 3D quadruped robot with 8 actuated joints. The goal is to coordinate the four legs to move forward as fast as possible. The reward includes distance traveled, a survival bonus and penalties for high control costs and contact forces.

- **HalfCheetah-v4**: A 2D bipedal robot with 6 actuated joints. The objective is to run forward as fast as possible. The reward is proportional to the forward velocity minus a control penalty.
- **Hopper-v4**: A 2D one-legged robot with 3 actuated joints. The agent must hop forward without falling. The reward combines forward velocity, a survival bonus and a control penalty.
- **Humanoid-v4**: A 3D bipedal robot with 17 actuated joints, simulating the human body. This is one of the most challenging tasks due to the high-dimensional state-action space and complex dynamics. The goal is to walk forward without falling.
- **InvertedPendulum-v4**: A cart-pole system where the pole must be balanced upright by moving the cart. The reward is constant for every step the pole remains upright.
- **Reacher-v4**: A 2-joint robot arm that must reach a random target position. The reward is based on the distance from the fingertip to the target and a control penalty.

C Implementation Details

We describe the detailed architecture and training configuration of FP-DRL. The algorithm combines a distributional soft actor-critic backbone with quantile regression and a Transformer-based flow matching policy.

Quantile Critic Network. The critic is an ensemble of two quantile networks. Each is a 3-layer MLP with 256 hidden units and BatchRenorm applied after each linear layer. The input to the critic is the concatenated state-action pair. Following the IQN formulation, the quantile fractions $\tau \in [0, 1]$ are first embedded using a cosine basis of dimension 64, projected to match the hidden dimension, and combined multiplicatively with the base features. The final layer outputs a scalar for each of the $N = 32$ quantiles. The quantile regression loss follows the Huber quantile loss with pairwise target comparisons:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{QR}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N \rho_{\tau_i}^{\kappa} (z_{\theta}(s, a; \tau_i) - \mathcal{T}z_{\bar{\theta}}(s', a'; \tau_j)) \cdot w_j, \quad (5)$$

where ρ_{τ}^{κ} is the asymmetric Huber loss, \mathcal{T} the distributional Bellman operator, and w_j the probability masses associated with the target quantiles. We use random quantile sampling with a small offset (IQN style) for both the current and target networks. The target distribution is computed using the minimum of the two target critics, and the CrossQ-style joint forward pass is employed: the current and next observations are concatenated to compute the Q -values in a single forward pass, reducing overestimation bias.

Transformer Flow Actor. The policy is a continuous normalizing flow (CNF) parameterized by a Transformer decoder. The observation $\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{S}|}$ is first encoded

through a two-layer MLP with SiLU activations and BatchRenorm to produce a context embedding $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{model}}}$. The flow operates in the unbounded action space $\mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{A}|}$ with a standard Gaussian base distribution $\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$. At each of the $K = 4$ Euler integration steps, the current state \mathbf{x}_k is augmented with a sinusoidal time embedding and processed by a stack of 2 Transformer decoder layers. Each layer consists of causal self-attention, cross-attention to \mathbf{c} , and a feed-forward network with GeLU activation.

The log-probability of the sampled action is computed via the instantaneous change-of-variables formula:

$$\log p(\mathbf{x}_K) = \log p(\mathbf{x}_0) - \sum_{k=1}^K \text{tr} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}_k}{\partial \mathbf{x}_k} \right) \Delta t, \quad (6)$$

where the trace is evaluated exactly by iterating over each action dimension and computing the Jacobian-vector product using forward-mode automatic differentiation. After the ODE integration, the final action is squashed to the valid range via $\mathbf{a} = \tanh(\mathbf{x}_K) \odot \sigma + \mu$, where σ and μ are the action scaling and bias derived from the environment bounds. The log-density is corrected for the tanh bijection as:

$$\log \pi(\mathbf{a}|\mathbf{s}) = \log p(\mathbf{x}_K) - \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{A}|} \log (\sigma_i(1 - \tanh^2(x_{K,i})) + \epsilon). \quad (7)$$

Batch Renormalization. We employ BatchRenorm with momentum 0.99 in both the actor and critic networks instead of standard BatchNorm. This mitigates the discrepancy between training and inference statistics and is critical for stable off-policy learning with distributional critics.

Entropy Regularization. The entropy coefficient α is automatically tuned to keep the policy entropy close to a target value $\bar{\mathcal{H}} = 0.0 \times |\mathcal{A}|$. The temperature is updated by minimizing:

$$\mathcal{L}(\alpha) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{s} \sim \mathcal{D}} [\alpha (-\log \pi(\mathbf{a}|\mathbf{s}) - \bar{\mathcal{H}})]. \quad (8)$$

D Hyperparameters

The complete set of hyperparameters used for the FP-DRL experiments is listed in Table 1. Values that differ across benchmark suites are described in the text; otherwise, the parameters are fixed for all tasks.

Notes:

- BatchRenorm is applied after every linear layer in both the critic and the actor’s observation encoder. The Transformer layers use LayerNorm internally.
- The actor’s encoder uses SiLU activations; the Transformer feed-forward blocks use GeLU.
- All experiments were run on a single NVIDIA GPU with JAX’s double-precision disabled and XLA preallocation turned off.

Table 1. Hyperparameters of FP-DRL for the Gymnasium MuJoCo benchmark.

Category	Parameter	Value
<i>General</i>	Update-to-data ratio	1
	Discount factor γ	0.99
	Batch size	512
	Replay buffer size	1×10^6
	Target smoothing τ	0.005
	Exploration steps	50,000
<i>Quantile Critic</i>	Number of critics	2
	Number of quantiles N	32
	Quantile embedding dim	64
	Hidden depth (per critic)	3
	Hidden size	256
	Learning rate	1×10^{-3}
	Optimizer	Adam ($\beta_1 = 0.5$)
	BatchRenorm momentum	0.99
<i>Transformer Flow Actor</i>	Denoising steps K	4
	Model dimension d_{model}	96
	Attention heads	4
	Transformer layers	2
	Learning rate	3×10^{-4}
	Optimizer	Adam ($\beta_1 = 0.5$)
	BatchRenorm momentum	0.99
<i>Entropy</i>	Initial α	0.2
	Automatic tuning	True
	Target entropy $\bar{\mathcal{H}}$	$0.0 \times \mathcal{A} $
	Learning rate (temperature)	1×10^{-3}
	Optimizer	Adam ($\beta_1 = 0.5$)
<i>Training</i>	Policy update delay	3 critic updates
	CrossQ joint forward	Enabled
	Risk type	neutral
	Tau sampling type	IQN (uniform + offset)